

A CASE STUDY ON GREEN ENVIRONMENT AND ECONOMIC GROWTH OF RWANDA

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1) ABSTRACT

Rwanda is a uniquely beautiful mountainous country located in central and east Africa, with wonderful biodiversity, national parks, and natural forests. Rwanda takes a holistic approach to green building design, recycling, and the efficient use of renewable energy. In order to achieve sustainable economic growth, Rwanda has taken great considerations on environmental sustainability and protection. Even if we look beyond agriculture, tourism, mineral wealth and fisheries, our economies depend critically on good environmental governance. For more than a decade, Rwanda has taken a practical approach and put environment and climate change at the heart of all the country's policies, programmes and plans. It was one of the first countries to ban plastic bags in 2008, and its commitment to nationwide landscape restoration is such that every year, millions of trees have been planted by Rwandans to protect the country's forests, rivers and wetlands and mountain slides. The plastic bag ban has earned the country a reputation as one of the cleanest in Africa. In 2008, capital Kigali of Rwanda, was declared by UN Habitat as one of the cleanest cities in Africa. It also created opportunities for entrepreneurs to invest in alternative packaging materials (cloths, papers, banana leaves and papyrus). This will help the country attract significant climate finance, enough to sustain rapid economic growth on a resource-saving, low carbon, and climate-resilient path. Rwanda will also benefit from a Green Climate Fund off-grid solar project that will promote the use of solar energy in East Africa through a new investment

fund, providing equity to clean Energy Company with expertise in household solar energy. Therefore, this study needs to explore about the green environment and growth of the country.

2) Keywords: Green environment, economic growth, green climate fund, and energy, FONERWA

3) Introduction

What is green environment?

Green Environment" relates to the concerns for environmental conservation and improved health of the environment. This includes

supporting practices like informed consumption, conservation practices and investment in renewable energy. **Economic growth** also refers to the increase in production of goods and services over a specific period of time. The aggregate economic growth is measured in terms of growth domestic product (GDP) or gross national product (GNP).

Rwandan economy and livelihood of her people are dependent on natural resources such as water, lands, air, animals and plants. These natural resources are increasing and Rwanda's economy was mainly grown by improving and protection of environment. The economic growth of the country was improved after the implementation and application of policies that protect environment as well as climate change. The promotion of green environment facilitated the growth of economy in different ways such as increase in agriculture productivity, revenue from tourism attraction especially those interested in visiting national parks and forests, exportation of agricultural products contributed a lot to the economic growth.

The protection and management of environment are among the pillars of Vision 2020. By 2020, the Government of Rwanda aim to have built a nation in which pressure on natural resources, particularly on land, water, biomass and biodiversity, has significantly been reduced and the process of environmental pollution and degradation has been reversed; a nation in which the management and protection of these resources and environment are more rational and well regulated in order to preserve and bequeath to future generations the basic wealth necessary for sustainable development

Along the journey of development, Rwanda has recognized the importance of environment and climate change in sustainable development. In 2003, the government of Rwanda adopted first-ever

environment policy to guide the management of environment and natural resources. The organic law N0 04/2005 determining the modalities of protection, conversation and promotion of environment as promulgated in April 2005 making a way for the management of environment .in 2006, law N0 16/2006 of 03/04/2006 was promulgated to determine the organization, functioning and responsibilities of Rwanda Environment Management Authority (REMA)

This case discusses about how Rwandan economic growth has been influenced by green environment polices implementation. Some of projects were implemented and still going on for the maintenance of health green environment as well as creation of jobs for many people, such projects are: Eco brigade programme, green Gicumbi, the use of electric cars as a way of reducing the importation of fuel for cars, green climate fund off-grid project and Rwanda's new green growth and climate resilience strategy, Go green Rwanda, Rwanda Air quality and climate change monitoring project and green growth solution.

4) Problem statement of the study

Rwanda as a small land locked country has experienced negative effect of inadequate environment maintenance strategies and mostly because of the nature of the country. Even if disasters still happening but they have already been reduced at a very high extent by the important policies and new strategies applied. How did the government of Rwanda use "green environment" to increase productivity which led to the economic growth of the country.

5) Literature review

Literature review will be presented of related literature with references to different sources of data and will discuss more about green environment and economic growth.

According to Lytle park.com Green Environment" relates to the concerns for environmental conservation and improved health of the environment. This includes supporting practices like informed consumption, conservation practices and investment in renewable energy.

According to Wikipedia Green climate fund is a fund established within the UNFCCC (United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change) as an operating entity of the financial mechanism to assist developing countries in adaptation and mitigation to counter climate change. The objective of green climate fund is to "**support projects**, programs, policies and other activities

in developing country parties using thematic funding windows. It is intended that the Green Climate Fund be the centerpiece of effort to raise climate finance under the UNFCCC.

According to Investopedia Economic growth is an increase in the production of economic goods and services, compared from one period of time to another. It can be measured in nominal or real (adjusted for inflation) terms.

FONERWA is the Rwanda 'green' fund. It is a cross sectoral financing mechanism for environment and climate change initiatives that further Rwanda's development objectives for environmentally sustainable, climate resilient and green economic growth. Access

to the fund is open to line ministries and districts, charitable and private entities, including businesses, civil society and research institutions. Preferences are given to legal entities from non-government and civil society organizations (NGOs/CSOs), local government, central governments, public colleges and universities, research and scientific bodies, as well as the private sector.

Projects must target priority areas for national development related to environment, climate change and green growth, FONERWA and carried out a formalized process of public calls for proposals (CFPs) presently scheduled every 6 month. During a one month window of opportunity, applicants submit their project concepts, known as Project profile Documents (PPDs), developed according to pre-established criteria.

In many ways the world in general and Rwanda in particular is vastly different than it was a decade ago and unexpected future changes can have a dramatic impact. Will changing socio-economic conditions threaten or sustain environmental good and services? Is our country prepared to cope with catastrophic events? What effect could major policy shifts and socio-economic developments on environment?

Environmental scenario planning helps envision a future very different from the present and develop concrete strategies that ensure success in the number of different reasonable futures (Alcamo 2001). It takes a broader and realistic approach that assesses today states and trends, explores tomorrow eventualities and prepares us for both. Through scenario planning we are also able to develop specific, measurable indicators that provide an early warning of what the future may bring and the opportunity to start preparing today (Detlef, Ochola and Riha 2008, Eastering et al. 2007, UNEP 2007). The goal of present Rwandan environmental scenario building the process

was to present insights into the national outlook, including short-term (up to 2025) scenarios for the major environmental issues addressed in the outlook report and possible policy responses. More specifically, the scenario building process of the outlook report was meant to achieve the following:

- Combine qualitative and quantitative information about the evolution of environmental challenges and opportunities in Rwanda
- Help REMA, other stakeholders, policy makers and experts to think big about the various environmental issues;
- Identify the strength of environmental policies under different future conditions · Illustrate how alternative policy pathways can achieve the environmental targets contained in the MDGs and the country vision 2020
- Provide picture of future alternative states of environment in the absence/presence of policies and thus illustrate impacts of society on the country's natural environment and point out the need for environmental policies to address the impacts
- Raise awareness about the future connection between different environmental challenge such as climate change and threats to biodiversity and human wellbeing.

6. Objective of Research

The main objective of this paper is to present the economic growth of Rwanda has been influenced by green environment maintenance.

7. Research methodology

This paper is based on secondary data gathered by the author. The new articles which are related to green environment and economic growth as well and the main focus, it looks to the extent at which economic growth was influenced by green environment.

8. Findings

In environmental terms, despite the high demographic pressure on land resources agriculture kept pace with environmental conversation spear-headed mainly by land consolidation, reduced human agricultural activities on wetland and other vulnerable lands. Soil erosion from riverbanks and nutrient loading in the water bodies such as the Nyabarongo river system and associated wetlands

had been adequately addressed through education and popular participation of land users. There is marked reduction in the proportion of the country's land disposed to erosion, from the 39.1% in 2009 to less than 10% on 2025.

Water

- Water crises on Rwanda lead to the extensive use adoption of water-efficiency technology · Water emerges as a catalytic crises that accelerate efforts to respond to climate change and to shift to new patterns of sustainable development.
- Water shortages and domestic tensions and international conflicts lessened **Chemicals**
- Chemicals production increases, but a shift occurs towards green chemistry. · Scientific progress makes possible major improvements in understanding the health and environmental impact of the chemicals in the environment.

Urban sprawl

- Development of green transportation and manufacturing systems slashes air pollution from mobile sources, but encourages continuation of auto- oriented, low-density development. · Nearly all problems associated with sprawl are checked- from loss of wetlands and fragmentation of ecosystems to escalating infrastructure costs and weakening of community life.

Biotechnology and nanotechnology

- Rwanda adopts biotechnology with shifts from **for** or **against** biotechnology to new concepts of alternative biotechnology development paths some of which are highly problematic while others are providing in terms of health and environmental impacts
- Nanotechnology is still on the horizon, but there is extensive discussion of potential uses for environmental remediation, clean energy, and zero-waste manufacturing

Climate change

- Shift toward higher energy efficiency, fuel cell, renewables and wellhead reforming of natural gas with CO₂ re-injection, begins to reduce CO₂ emissions
- Rwanda joins affluent nations in serious efforts minimize climate change

So what else Rwanda is doing to for environment that improves and promote economic growth

Plastic bags

Plastic ban has earned the country reputation as one of the cleanest countries in Africa. In 2008 Rwanda's capital, Kigali was declared one of the cleanest cities in Africa by UN Habitat. It also created opportunities for entrepreneurs who invested in alternative packaging materials (cloths, papers, banana leaves and papyrus).

Forest cover

To achieve its goals of increasing forest cover of 30% of total land area by 2020, Rwanda has embarked on massive reforestation and tree-planting drive, and new measures such as agroforestry and training schemes in forest management are being implemented. These efforts, along with the plastic-bag ban, earned the nation a Fund Policy Award from World Future in 2011.

Restoration

Rwanda's commitment to conserve the environment has also been seen through the protection and restoration of degraded ecosystems such as wetlands, lakes and natural forests. Forests such as Nyungwe, Gishwati and Mukura have been restored and upgraded into national parks. The promotion of these parks, home to a vast variety of flora and fauna, has contributed to the growth of the tourism sector that is currently the principal generator of foreign currency, with US \$ 304.9 million and US \$318 million revenue in 2014 and 2015 respectively.

The Green Fund

As one of the most vulnerable nations to climate change, Rwanda is extremely aware of the challenges that lies ahead therefore, to

achieve its vision of a low-carbon and climate-resilient economy by 2050, Rwanda has established the **Green Fund**, a groundbreaking investment fund, the largest of its kind in Africa.

The fund supports the best public and private projects that have the potential for transformative change which supported Rwanda's commitment to building a green economy.

The fund has mobilized around \$100 million to date and is a leading example of the impact that well-managed climate financing can have.

Green politics

As a growing nation, Rwanda has the opportunity to bypass old technologies and environmentally destructive development and build an economy that can withstand a changing climate and that provides prosperity for generations to come. Green economy and green jobs is part of the strategies. This involves the development of industry, services, eco-tourism, agriculture, and jobs promoting sustainable, least impactful, low-carbon, ecosystem protecting, resource conservation and waste/pollution reduction and recycling technologies and practices.

Thanks to Rwanda's efforts to put the environment and climate change at the heart of her development, the country's Ministry of Natural Resources was recently accredited by the International Green Climate Fund. This will help the country attract significant climate finance, enough to enable it to maintain rapid economic growth on a resource-efficient, low-carbon and climate-resilient path. This strategy looks beyond 2020 to 2050, and recommends actions that Rwanda can take in the short to medium term to ensure its future stability and prosperity in a changing climate and uncertain energy future. The purpose of the strategy is threefold: (1) To guide national policy and planning in an integrated way, (2) To mainstream climate change into all sectors of the economy, and (3) To position countries to access international funding to achieve climate resilience and low carbon development. The strategy calls upon national planners to chart a new development pathway for integrated sector planning that balances cross cutting issues of resource management.

9. Conclusion

All these initiatives are being built on the past successful stories in environmental sustainability in Rwanda. For instance, ten years ago, the Rwandan Government banned plastic bags use in the country. The implementation of this decision was so successful that

today many countries would like to know how Rwanda made it possible to achieve this commendable environmental friendly milestone. Today, the whole World is making decisions to "beat plastic pollution".

Although, the economic growth of Rwanda depends on different sectors such as services or industrial sector but green environment should be taken into consideration like how it is being implemented and its positive effects should be lesson to other nations. Green growth strategies tend to be most effective where they link strong and credible planning, analysis, implementation, and monitoring processes in an iterative and reinforcing cycle and with active stakeholder engagement. And to ensure that green development brings up its desired results, national and local governments need to make informed choices from a deep pool of experience and learning.

In a context of high defenselessness to climate change, strong reliance on rain-fed agriculture, dependency on hydropower for half of national electricity generation, and endeavors to preserve our natural ecosystems and biodiversity, integrating adaptation to the effects of climate change with green growth emerged as a major barrier in developing the strategy. This was made more difficult by the limited understanding of the new concept of green growth against the business as usual development pattern for a country with very low emissions production patterns. Every human being should be responsible for the maintenance of green environment that attracts foreign investment and generate revenue from tourism industry.

10. Recommendation

To present a more comprehensive understanding of the topic, future bibliometric studies in the area of green products may examine various non-indexed journals and other available databases like Web of Science, Google Scholar. The researchers in the future may achieve better results by comparing various interchangeably used terms like "green environment", "sustainable products", "environmental products", "ecological products", and "eco-products", and analyzing extracted data against each of these terms

individually. More cooperation and partnership will be needed to mobilize financial resources and develop the required multi-sectoral and inter disciplinary capacity to accelerate the speed of the journey towards the Climate Resilient Rwanda.

Reference

1. Alcamo, J. (2001). Scenarios as tools for international environmental assessment. European Environment Agency, Copenhagen.
2. Detlef, P. Vuuren, V., Ochola, W.O. and S. Riha. (2008). Outlook on Global Agricultural Change and its Drivers: Chapter 4 in the International Assessment of Agricultural Science and technology for Development (IAASTD). The World Bank, Washington DC.
3. Easterling, W.E., Aggarwal, P.K., Batima, P., Brander, K.M., Erda, L., Howden, S.M., Kirilenko, A., Morton, J., Soussana, J.F., Schmidhuber, J., and F.N. Tubiello (2007). Food, fibre and forest products. Contribution of Working Group II to the Fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, ed. M.L. Parry, O.F. Canziani, J.P. Palutikof, P.J. van der Linden and C.E. Hanson. Cambridge, U.K.: Cambridge University Press.
4. https://cdkn.org/project/a-strategic-framework-for-rwanda/?loclang=en_gb